

Cellphonia: WET

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Biographical information

In 2006 Bull's Hot-n-Cold GPS game made NAVTEQ LBS Challenge finalist, his New-York Historical Society Slavery Tour launched on vodcast, podcast and VOIP, the NYTimes reviewed Cellphonia: San Jose at ISEA ZeroOne, and two telephone pieces played in Peter Stuyvesant's Ghost. Svoboda's opera WET premiered at L.A.'s Disney Hall in 2005. Gresham-Lancaster has worked in network music, telematic performance, multimedia prototyping and user interface theory and is a member of the Hub. Mintchev is a classically trained musician from the Belles-Artes, Mexico City and works as a new media designer and coder in New York City.

Description of Piece

Cellphonia: WET is an ongoing Do-It-Yourself (DIY) post-modern single-song opera about the world's water crisis where the participants sing karaoke style into their cellphones and the resulting performance of all singers is mixed and delivered as an interactive sound/video installation. Visitors see projected info about the lack of fresh water in the world over wet imagery while hearing the Naiads' Lament performed by previous callers. At the end of the song, they hear an audio tag and see a flashing phone number inviting them to use their cellphones to sing along or join the Drip Chorus and make water noises. The callers' voices are automatically added to the four-minute looping performance. For people who are not at the venue, handouts, posters hung around the city, and the accompanying website give them directions how to add their own voices to the opera.